

Next Generation Sequencing		Isolation						
Sample (Colony number)	16S rRNA Library Read Pairs/Classified	Shannon (H')	Simpson (C)	16S rRNA Library Order / Genus (% Reads)	Order / Genus	nifH	Growth on N-free medium	Found in the 16S rRNA Library [Identity (read %)] #
<i>Atta laevigata</i> Sanitized (Rio Claro)	108,938 / 99.87%	2.724	0.8502	Rhizobiales / <i>Liberibacter</i> (88.58) Rhizobiales / <i>Terasakiella</i> (1.3) Rhodobacterales / <i>Rhodovulum</i> (0.5)	Rhizobiales / <i>Methylobacterium</i> Burkholderiales / <i>Ralstonia</i> Actinomycetales / <i>Brachybacterium</i> Pseudomonadales / <i>Acinetobacter</i>	+ + - -	-/+ + - -	86.7 - 94.2 (7.2) No 83.8 - 93.6 (0.006) 94.7 - 98.6 (0.017)
<i>Atta laevigata</i> (Rio Claro)	126,678 / 99.77%	3.688	0.9406	Rhizobiales / <i>Liberibacter</i> (89.45) Rhodobacterales / <i>Rhodovulum</i> (0.78)				
<i>Atta sexdens</i> Sanitized (Rio Claro)	82,680 / 99.9%	3.016	0.8298	Rhizobiales / <i>Bartonella</i> (92.98) Rhodobacterales / <i>Rhodovulum</i> (1.48) Rhizobiales / <i>Liberibacter</i> (1.17)	Burkholderiales / <i>Ralstonia</i> Rhizobiales / <i>Methylobacterium</i> Pseudomonadales / <i>Acinetobacter</i>	+ + -	+ + -	91.5 - 93.9 (0.008) 94.7 - 99.1 (0.59) No
<i>Atta sexdens</i> (Rio Claro)	124,222 / 99.73%	3.263	0.8532	Rhizobiales / <i>Bartonella</i> (80.3) Rhodobacterales / <i>Rhodovulum</i> (1.56) Rhizobiales / <i>Liberibacter</i> (1.1)				
<i>Acromyrmex rugosus</i> Sanitized (Rio Claro)	106,078 / 99.97%	0.84	0.4828	Entomoplasmatales / <i>Mesoplasma</i> (56.42) Rhizobiales / <i>Terasakiella</i> (27.56) Entomoplasmatales / <i>Entomoplasma</i> (5.84) Rhizobiales / <i>Liberibacter</i> (3.2) Rhodobacterales / <i>Rhodovulum</i> (2.27) Entomoplasmatales / <i>Spiroplasma</i> (1.15)	Pseudomonadales / <i>Acinetobacter</i> Pseudomonadales / <i>Pseudomonas</i>	- +	- -/+	No No
<i>Acromyrmex rugosus</i> (Rio Claro)	119,161 / 99.98%	1.249	0.5944	Entomoplasmatales / <i>Mesoplasma</i> (33.73) Rhizobiales / <i>Terasakiella</i> (32.57) Rhizobiales / <i>Bartonella</i> (9.66) Rhizobiales / <i>Liberibacter</i> (8.76) Entomoplasmatales / <i>Entomoplasma</i> (3.34) Rhodobacterales / <i>Rhodovulum</i> (2.33) Entomoplasmatales / <i>Spiroplasma</i> (1.11)				
<i>Acromyrmex coronatus</i> Sanitized (Rio Claro)	100,217 / 99.97%	0.916	0.4868	Rhizobiales / <i>Terasakiella</i> (56.21) Entomoplasmatales / <i>Mesoplasma</i> (25.72) Rhizobiales / <i>Liberibacter</i> (5.69) Entomoplasmatales / <i>Entomoplasma</i> (3.02) Rhodobacterales / <i>Rhodovulum</i> (2.4) Entomoplasmatales / <i>Spiroplasma</i> (0.96)	Pseudomonadales / <i>Acinetobacter</i> Burkholderiales / <i>Ralstonia</i>	- +	- +	92.9 - 93.3 (0.11) No
<i>Acromyrmex coronatus</i> (Rio Claro)	98,703 / 99.96%	0.948	0.5223	Entomoplasmatales / <i>Mesoplasma</i> (50.93) Rhizobiales / <i>Terasakiella</i> (31.81) Entomoplasmatales / <i>Entomoplasma</i> (5.35) Rhizobiales / <i>Liberibacter</i> (3.49) Rhodobacterales / <i>Rhodovulum</i> (2.36) Entomoplasmatales / <i>Spiroplasma</i> (1.41)				

<i>Atta laevigata</i>	Rhizobiales / <i>Methylobacterium</i>	+	-/+
Sanitized	Burkholderiales / <i>Ralstonia</i>	+	+
(Itirapina)	Pseudomonadales / <i>Acinetobacter</i>	-	-

Table 1. Bacteria identified in the leafcutter abdomen by 16S rRNA sequencing or isolation methods. # Read %: percentage of library reads mapped on a given 16S rRNA sanger read as obtained by Bowtie2.